

Recent Research in Acupuncture for Depression: An Overview and Methodological Analysis of Controlled Trials.

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Abstract: Depression is a prevalent condition with a significant impact on affect, cognition, and daily functioning, affecting individuals globally across all demographics. While conventional treatments exist, a substantial portion of patients do not achieve adequate response or experience side effects, highlighting the need for exploring alternative therapeutic options. Acupuncture, rooted in traditional Chinese medicine, has shown potential in modulating biological pathways relevant to depression. This paper aims to synthesise findings from recent randomised controlled trials on the effectiveness of acupuncture for depression and analyse the acupuncture methodologies employed. Therefore, a literature search was conducted in PubMed and SciELO to identify randomised controlled trials published between 2020 and 2025 that evaluated acupuncture as an intervention for depression. The initial search yielded 41 records, with no duplicates. After screening, 31 articles were excluded, and 2 full-text articles could not be retrieved. Eight randomised controlled trials met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis. These studies investigated the efficacy of acupuncture and electroacupuncture in diverse populations, including individuals with post-stroke depression, chronic insomnia, depression in hemodialysis patients, and fibromyalgia. The most frequently used acupuncture points were GV20 and SP6, often in combination, with electroacupuncture commonly applied between GV20 and GV29. The reviewed randomised controlled trials provide promising evidence for the effectiveness and safety of acupuncture and electroacupuncture in alleviating depressive symptoms and improving associated outcomes such as sleep quality, cognitive function, and quality of life across various conditions. Mechanistic insights from these studies and preclinical research suggest that acupuncture may exert its effects through modulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, enhancement of neuroplasticity via BDNF signalling, and regulation of neuroendocrine and metabolic pathways. The frequent use of specific acupoints like GV20 and SP6 aligns with traditional Chinese medicine patterns associated with depression. However, limitations such as methodological heterogeneity, small sample sizes, and short follow-up periods necessitate further rigorous research to optimise treatment protocols, elucidate underlying mechanisms, and identify patient-specific predictors of response for effective clinical integration.

Keywords: Depression; Acupuncture; Acupuncture Points; Traditional Chinese Medicine.

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1. Introduction

According to the National Institute of Mental Health ¹, depression can manifest with significant symptomatology impacting affect, cognition, and the capacity to execute routine daily functions, including sleep, alimentation, and occupational tasks. This condition

exhibits a universal prevalence, affecting individuals across all demographic strata, irrespective of age, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, cultural background, or educational attainment. Current research implicates a confluence of genetic, biological, environmental, and psychological determinants in the aetiology of depression²⁻⁸.

Recent data from the World Health Organization (WHO) in 2019 estimated that around 280 million people worldwide, representing about 5% of all adults, experienced depression. In the United States, the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH) reported that in 2021, approximately 21 million adults (8.3% of all U.S. adults) had experienced at least one major depressive episode. Depression is more common among women than men and has a higher prevalence among younger adults. The impact of depression extends beyond individual suffering, contributing to significant social and economic burdens through reduced productivity, impaired social functioning, and increased risk of suicide^{1,9-11}.

Conventional treatments for depression typically include pharmacological interventions, primarily with antidepressant medications, and various forms of psychotherapy, such as cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) and interpersonal therapy (IPT). While these treatments are effective for many individuals, a significant portion of patients may not respond adequately or experience side effects^{11,12}. This highlights the need for exploring and evaluating other potential treatment options to help address this gap.

The interest in acupuncture as a treatment for depression stems from its long history of use in traditional Chinese medicine for various physical and mental health conditions. From a mechanistic perspective, research suggests that acupuncture may influence several biological pathways relevant to depression. These include the regulation of neurotransmitter levels (such as serotonin, dopamine, and endorphins), modulation of the neuroendocrine axis (including the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis involved in stress response), improvement of neuroplasticity (the brain's ability to adapt and form new connections), and anti-inflammatory effects¹³⁻¹⁶. By acting on these systems, acupuncture may help to improve emotional state and alleviate depressive symptoms.

This paper aims to synthesise findings from recent randomised controlled trials on the effectiveness of acupuncture for depression while also detailing and analysing the acupuncture methodologies used within these studies.

2. Methods

A literature search was conducted to identify studies evaluating the effectiveness of acupuncture as a sole intervention for the treatment of depression. The search was carried out in two major electronic databases: PubMed and SciELO. The search strategy included the following terms: (acupuncture[Title/Abstract]) AND (depression[Title]) AND ((RCT[Publication Type] OR "randomized controlled trial"[Title/Abstract])) AND ((effectiveness[Title/Abstract] OR efficacy[Title/Abstract] OR outcome[Title/Abstract] OR treatment[Title/Abstract])).

To ensure the relevance of the included studies, specific inclusion criteria were applied. Only studies published within the last five years, from 2020 to 2025, were considered. Eligible articles had to be written in Portuguese, Spanish, or English. Furthermore, only studies designed as randomised controlled trials were included in the review. Finally, studies should have assessed acupuncture as a therapeutic intervention for depression.

Titles and abstracts were screened for relevance, and full texts were reviewed for eligibility based on the above criteria. Duplicate records were removed, and only studies meeting all inclusion parameters were retained for analysis.

3. Results

Figure 1 presents the articles' search and selection details.

Figure 1. Flowchart of study selection.

The initial search yielded 41 records through database searches. No duplicates were found; therefore, 41 studies were screened.

Following title and abstract screening, 31 records were excluded based on relevance, leaving 10 full-text articles for detailed assessment. Of these, 2 were excluded for inability to retrieve them, resulting in 8 studies that met the inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis.

4. Discussion

4.1. Clinical efficacy and safety

This section summarises the key findings from the included studies.

Cai *et al.*¹⁷ provided strong evidence supporting the efficacy and safety of electroacupuncture as a therapeutic option for post-stroke depression (PSD). Patients in the electroacupuncture group experienced significant improvements across various clinical outcomes, including the Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression (HRSD), Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS), National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS), Barthel Index (BI), and Traditional Chinese Medicine syndrome scores (all $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that electroacupuncture can effectively reduce depressive symptoms while also promoting neurological recovery and functional independence following stroke.

Further comparisons with a sham electroacupuncture group reinforced these results. At weeks 2, 4, and 8, HRSD scores were consistently lower in the electroacupuncture group compared to controls ($F = 31.33, 35.58, \text{ and } 25.03$, respectively; all $p < 0.001$), highlighting a robust antidepressant effect. Similar significant improvements were observed in SDS, NIHSS, and BI scores, indicating that electroacupuncture also benefits motor function and activities of daily living. In terms of safety, electroacupuncture was well tolerated, with only two mild cases of local hematoma reported and no serious adverse events.

Together, these findings position electroacupuncture as a promising adjunct or alternative treatment for PSD, facilitating both psychological and functional recovery. Nonetheless, larger studies with longer follow-up periods are necessary to validate these outcomes and investigate the underlying mechanisms.

In a related context, Liu *et al.*¹⁸ examined the efficacy of acupuncture in improving sleep quality and reducing anxiety and depression among patients with chronic insomnia. Their results demonstrated that acupuncture significantly decreased serum cortisol levels and increased serum serotonin (5-HT) concentrations compared to sham acupuncture, suggesting modulation of neuroendocrine pathways involved in stress and mood regulation. Clinically, the acupuncture group showed significantly greater and more durable improvements in Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAMA), and Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) scores at treatment completion and follow-up, whereas the sham group exhibited less pronounced and less sustained effects.

These findings imply that dysregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and serotonergic function may contribute to mood disturbances in chronic insomnia, with acupuncture potentially exerting therapeutic effects by restoring these physiological processes. The sustained benefits observed highlight acupuncture's potential as a reliable non-pharmacological intervention for mood and sleep disturbances in chronic insomnia. Further research with larger cohorts and a mechanistic focus is warranted.

Yu *et al.*¹⁹ explored acupuncture as an adjunctive therapy for mild to moderate depression in hemodialysis patients. Treatment led to significant reductions in Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) scores and improvements in quality of life, alongside favourable changes in biochemical markers such as serum albumin, haemoglobin, transferrin, and total protein levels. Multivariable regression analysis identified acupuncture ($P = 0.004$) and serum albumin levels ($P = 0.03$) as significant predictors of symptom improvement, with the model explaining 45% of variance (adjusted $R^2 = 0.45$). Although other biochemical markers showed modest post-treatment gains, they did not independently predict depression outcomes.

These results suggest that nutritional and metabolic status, particularly serum albumin, may influence psychological responses to acupuncture in this vulnerable population. Importantly, no serious adverse events were reported, indicating that acupuncture is a safe and well-tolerated treatment for hemodialysis patients with depression. This study supports incorporating acupuncture into multidisciplinary care plans, with further research needed to elucidate mechanisms, long-term efficacy, optimal dosing, and interactions with other therapies.

Similarly, Yin *et al.*²⁰ demonstrated that electroacupuncture significantly improves sleep quality in patients with depression. The electroacupuncture group showed greater reductions in Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) scores compared to two control groups over the 8-week treatment period, with mean reductions of -6.64 points versus -2.23 and -2.94 points in controls (95% CI = -5.74 to -2.39 and -5.73 to -2.47 , respectively). Improvements were also noted in sleep efficiency (SE) and total sleep time (TST), both showing statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, reductions in depression and anxiety scores (HAMD-17, SDS, HAMA) suggested broader therapeutic effects on mood and sleep regulation.

However, no significant between-group differences were observed for sleep activity (SA) scores at treatment end ($p = 0.24$ and 0.08), indicating that while electroacupuncture improves overall sleep quality, its impact on specific sleep architecture components may be limited. These findings support electroacupuncture's clinical utility as an adjunctive insomnia treatment in depression, emphasising its multifaceted benefits. Further investigation into long-term effects and mechanisms is warranted.

Addressing cognitive impairment post-stroke, Zhang *et al.*²¹ compared interactive dynamic scalp acupuncture (IDSA) with simple combination therapy (SCT) and traditional scalp acupuncture (TSA). At baseline, all groups had comparable cognitive, mood,

sleep, and functional scores. From the second month onward (M2–M4), the IDSA group showed significantly greater improvements in Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE), Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA), and Modified Barthel Index (MBI) scores, reflecting enhanced cognition and self-care ability.

Concurrently, depression, anxiety, and sleep disturbance scores (HAMD, HAMA, PSQI) were significantly reduced in the IDSA group, with a greater magnitude of change from baseline compared to SCT and TSA, except for HAMD at M4–M0. By M2, IDSA patients exhibited significantly lower severity across cognitive, emotional, sleep, and functional domains (all $p < 0.01$). No serious adverse events were reported, underscoring IDSA's safety and tolerability.

Overall, these results indicate that IDSA offers superior therapeutic benefits to conventional scalp acupuncture or combination therapies for post-stroke cognitive impairment, supporting further research into its mechanisms and potential integration into neurorehabilitation protocols.

The randomised controlled trial by Li *et al.*²² investigated electroacupuncture combined with antidepressants versus antidepressants alone in depression treatment. Patients receiving combined therapy exhibited significantly greater reductions in Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) scores at weeks 4, 8, and 12 (all $P < .001$), suggesting faster and more sustained antidepressant effects.

Urinary metabolomic analysis revealed significant alterations in metabolites involved in fatty acid biosynthesis (malonic acid), glutamate metabolism (cysteine, glutathione, proline), and tryptophan metabolism (tryptophan, N-acetyl-5-hydroxytryptamine). These biochemical changes implicate electroacupuncture in modulating neurotransmission, neuroinflammation, and cellular energy pathways relevant to depression pathophysiology.

Given the role of tryptophan as a serotonin precursor and glutamate in neuroplasticity, electroacupuncture's effects on these metabolic systems may underlie its synergistic action with pharmacotherapy. These findings support incorporating electroacupuncture into depression management and warrant further exploration of its metabolic mechanisms and potential biomarkers of treatment response.

Similarly, Wang *et al.*²³ assessed acupuncture at ghost points combined with fluoxetine for mild to moderate depression. While no significant differences in depression scales were seen at 4 weeks, the acupuncture group exhibited significantly lower Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HAMD) and Self-Rating Depression Scale (SDS) scores at 8 weeks ($P < 0.05$), indicating a more pronounced and sustained symptom reduction.

Neuroimaging using fractional Amplitude of Low Frequency Fluctuations (fALFF) revealed decreased activity in the left anterior wedge leaf, posterior cingulate gyrus, and occipital gyri, alongside increased activity in the right inferior frontal gyrus, insula, and hippocampus (all $P < 0.05$). These regions are critical for emotional processing and cognitive control, suggesting that acupuncture may modulate neural circuits involved in depression.

Moreover, the effective rate was higher in the acupuncture group (51.25%) compared to controls (36.25%) after 8 weeks ($P < 0.05$), highlighting the clinical advantage of combined treatment. The delayed onset of significant effects suggests cumulative benefits with sustained acupuncture administration. These findings advocate for acupuncture as a valuable complement to pharmacotherapy, with further research needed to elucidate mechanisms and long-term outcomes.

Lastly, Garrido-Ardila *et al.*²⁴ compared core stability physiotherapy and acupuncture in women with fibromyalgia, focusing on quality of life, pain, joint stiffness, work-related difficulties, and depression. Both interventions yielded descriptive improvements across outcomes at weeks 6 and 13 relative to baseline; however, these changes were not statistically significant when compared to controls.

At week 6, mean Spanish Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire (FIQ) scores were 62.89 ± 16.91 for physiotherapy, 62.5 ± 18.09 for acupuncture, and 67.45 ± 17.07 for controls,

suggesting potential clinical relevance despite lack of significance. Notably, a minor decrease in “difficulty to work” was observed in the acupuncture group at week 13, indicating possible delayed or variable response in this domain.

Overall, these findings suggest that while both interventions may offer modest symptom relief, neither demonstrated robust efficacy within the study timeframe. This highlights the need for larger, longer-term studies and exploration of combination therapies to optimise treatment for this multifaceted condition.

Collectively, these studies provide compelling evidence supporting acupuncture and electroacupuncture as effective, safe, and well-tolerated interventions across a range of neuropsychiatric and chronic conditions, including post-stroke depression, chronic insomnia, depression in hemodialysis patients, and fibromyalgia-related symptoms. The findings consistently demonstrate improvements in mood, cognitive function, sleep quality, and functional outcomes, often accompanied by favourable biochemical and neurophysiological changes.

Electroacupuncture, in particular, shows promise in enhancing recovery post-stroke, modulating neuroendocrine and metabolic pathways implicated in depression, and augmenting the efficacy of conventional pharmacotherapy. Similarly, acupuncture appears to positively influence neurobiological substrates such as the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis and serotonergic system, contributing to sustained symptomatic relief in anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances.

Despite these encouraging results, several studies highlight limitations such as small sample sizes, short follow-up durations, and heterogeneous methodologies. Moreover, while some interventions showed trends toward clinical benefit, statistical significance was not always achieved, underscoring the need for larger, rigorously designed randomised controlled trials.

Future research should focus on elucidating the underlying mechanisms of acupuncture’s therapeutic effects, optimising treatment protocols, and exploring long-term outcomes. Integrating acupuncture into multidisciplinary care may offer a valuable adjunctive approach, particularly for patients with complex or treatment-resistant conditions.

4.2. Acupuncture methodologies analysis

Several acupuncture methodologies were employed across the included studies. Figure 2 presents the frequency of use for specific acupuncture points.

Among the 22 acupuncture points reported, GV20 and SP6 were the most frequently used (each in 5 of 8 studies), followed by GV29, HT7, and ST36 (each used in 3 studies).

Figure 2. Frequency of acupuncture point usage across included studies.

Beyond individual point usage, we analysed concurrent point combinations and identified several recurring patterns. Specifically, the combination of GV20 and GV29 was

used in three studies, all employing electroacupuncture to connect these two points. The detailed methodologies for this electroacupuncture protocol are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Electroacupuncture protocols for the GV20 + GV29 combination.

GV20 + GV24 electroacupuncture		
30 minutes, 2 Hz continuous wave stimulation.	30 minutes, 30Hz continuous wave stimulation.	30 minutes, 10Hz continuous wave stimulation.
18	20	22

Other commonly observed 2-point combinations included GV20 + SP6 (4 studies) and SP6 + GV29 (3 studies). Of particular interest was a frequently used 3-point combination of GV20, GV29, and SP6 (3 studies), with electroacupuncture applied between GV20 and GV29.

Expanding further, a 4-point combination comprising GV20, GV29, SP6, and HT7 was observed in 3 studies, while a 5-point combination including PC6 in addition to the above was identified in 2 studies.

The following Table (Table 2) synthesises the information regarding these combinations.

Table 2. Acupuncture point combinations and frequency across studies

Combinations	Studies
GV20 + SP6	22, 20, 18, 17
GV20 +* GV29 + SP6	22, 20, 18
GV20 +* GV29 + SP6 + HT7	22, 20, 18
GV20 +* GV29 + SP6 + HT7 + PC6	22, 20

*Acupuncture points connected via electroacupuncture.

4.3. Theoretical Rationale and traditional Chinese medicine Patterns

According to traditional Chinese medicine, depression has multifactorial origins. Maciocia²⁵ attributes its aetiology to emotional stress (anger, sadness and grief, worry, and guilt), constitutional traits, poor dietary habits, and overwork. Many of the acupuncture points used in the included studies correspond to specific depression-related traditional Chinese medicine patterns as summarised in Table 3.

Although GV29 is not directly associated with a specific pattern in Maciocia's framework, it is traditionally employed to calm the mind and improve sleep quality²⁶. Since electroacupuncture requires point pairs, GV29 is a practical complement to GV20 for neuromodulatory effects.

Of note, GV20 is associated with 9 out of 13 depression-related traditional Chinese medicine patterns, underscoring its central role. SP6, HT7, and PC6 complement GV20, together covering all 13 patterns.

4.4 Mechanistic Insights from Preclinical and Clinical Studies

A preclinical study²⁷, showed that electroacupuncture at GV20 exerted neuroprotective effects against chronic unpredictable mild stress chronic unpredictable mild stress by enhancing BDNF expression and promoting hippocampal neurogenesis. Similarly, Gao *et al.*²⁸ demonstrated that stimulation of GV20, GV29, LI4, and LR3 improved depressive symptoms in chronic unpredictable mild stress models via upregulation of BDNF/mTORC1 signalling and synaptic plasticity markers such as PSD95, Synapsin I, and GluR1.

Table 3. Correspondence of acupuncture points to traditional Chinese medicine depression patterns (Maciocia²⁵)

Patterns	GV20	GV29	SP6	HT7	PC6
Liver-Qi stagnation	X				X
Stagnant Liver-Qi turning into heat	X				X
Phlegm-Heat harassing the mind	X		X		
Blood Stasis obstructing the mind	X		X		X
Qi Stagnation with Phlegm	X		X		X
Worry injuring the mind	X				
Heart and Spleen Deficiency	X		X		
Heart-Yang Deficiency	X		X		
Kidney-Yang Deficiency	X				
Kidney- and Heart-Yin Deficiency with empty Heat blazing			X		
Heart- and Lung-Qi stagnation				X	X
Heart and Spleen Deficiency				X	X
Diaphragm Heat					X

The complexity of depression, as recognised in both traditional Chinese medicine and Western medicine, was also reflected in a study by Zhou *et al.*²⁹ where electroacupuncture at ST36 and SP6 alleviated anxiety and depression-like behaviours in colitis model rats. The therapeutic effects were attributed to modulation of the gut-brain axis, including hippocampal inflammation, metabolic homeostasis, and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis regulation.

In a related domain, Liu *et al.*³⁰ identified GV29 and HT7 as frequently used acupuncture points for managing depression, anxiety, and stress. HT7, a key point for calming the mind and nourishing the Shen, has been shown to reduce sympathetic nervous activity and regulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, along with increasing BDNF expression in the brain³¹⁻³³. GV29, likewise, has demonstrated anxiolytic properties via central nervous system modulation³⁴. This pairing provides a holistic approach addressing both psychological well-being and physiological balance.

Further, Du *et al.*³⁵ reported that electroacupuncture at HT7 and SP6 using dilational 5/25 Hz waveforms significantly improved sleep and consciousness regulation by lowering serum norepinephrine levels.

Supporting the inclusion of PC6, Kim *et al.*³⁶ demonstrated its efficacy in reversing biochemical and behavioural impairments in chronic stress models. Additionally, stimulation of PC6 attenuated symptoms of a hypoactive hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis in corticosterone-induced depression models³⁷.

Finally, consistent with our findings, Huang³⁸ identified GV20 and PC6 as the most frequently used acupuncture points in the treatment of depression.

5. Conclusions

This review analysed recent randomised controlled trials investigating the efficacy and methodology of acupuncture for the treatment of depression. Across diverse patient populations (including individuals with post-stroke depression, chronic insomnia, hemodialysis-related depression, and fibromyalgia), acupuncture and electroacupuncture demonstrated promising clinical outcomes. The studies consistently reported reductions in depression and anxiety scores, improvements in sleep quality, cognitive function, and overall quality of life, with few adverse effects.

Electroacupuncture emerged as a particularly effective modality, frequently applied to acupoint combinations such as GV20 plus GV29, SP6, HT7, and PC6. These points align with multiple traditional Chinese medicine diagnostic patterns and have been supported

by mechanistic studies implicating modulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, enhancement of neuroplasticity via BDNF signalling, and neuroendocrine and metabolic regulation. Neuroimaging and biomarker analyses further reinforce acupuncture's capacity to influence central and peripheral mechanisms relevant to depression.

Nonetheless, heterogeneity in methodologies, small sample sizes, and short treatment durations limit the generalizability of findings. Variability in acupuncture point selection, stimulation parameters, and outcome measures underscores the need for greater standardisation in future trials.

In sum, acupuncture represents a safe and potentially effective therapeutic strategy for depression, either as a standalone intervention or as an adjunct to conventional treatments. Continued research should prioritise elucidating biological mechanisms, optimising treatment protocols, and exploring patient-specific predictors of response to inform clinical integration.

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References

1. National Institute of Mental Health. What is depression? [updated December 2024. Available from: <https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/topics/depression#hts-intro>
2. Lohoff FW. Overview of the genetics of major depressive disorder. *Current psychiatry reports*. 2010;12(6):539-46. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11920-010-0150-6>
3. Duman RS, Sanacora G, Krystal JH. Altered Connectivity in Depression: GABA and Glutamate Neurotransmitter Deficits and Reversal by Novel Treatments. *Neuron*. 2019;102(1):75-90. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuron.2019.03.013>
4. Keller J, Gomez R, Williams G, Lembke A, Lazzeroni L, Murphy GM, Jr., et al. HPA axis in major depression: cortisol, clinical symptomatology and genetic variation predict cognition. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2017;22(4):527-36. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2016.120>
5. Pastis I, Santos MG, Paruchuri A. Exploring the role of inflammation in major depressive disorder: beyond the monoamine hypothesis. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*. 2024;Volume 17 - 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2023.1282242>
6. Reuben A, Manczak EM, Cabrera LY, Alegria M, Bucher ML, Freeman EC, et al. The Interplay of Environmental Exposures and Mental Health: Setting an Agenda. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2022;130(2):25001. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp9889>
7. Luyten P, Sabbe B, Blatt SJ, Meganck S, Jansen B, De Grave C, et al. Dependency and self-criticism: relationship with major depressive disorder, severity of depression, and clinical presentation. *Depress Anxiety*. 2007;24(8):586-96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/da.20272>
8. Quinn ME, E. GK, and Adam EK. Negative cognitive style and cortisol recovery accentuate the relationship between life stress and depressive symptoms. *Stress*. 2018;21(2):119-27. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10253890.2017.1414800>

9. World Health Organization. Depression and Other Common Mental Disorders: Global Health Estimates. Geneva 2017.
10. World Health Organization. Depressive disorder (depression) 2023 [Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/depression>]
11. The National Institute of Mental Health. Depression [updated 2024. Available from: <https://www.nimh.nih.gov/health/publications/depression/index.shtml>]
12. National Health Service. Treatment - Depression in adults [updated 5 July 2023. Available from: <https://www.nhs.uk/mental-health/conditions/depression-in-adults/treatment/>]
13. Li P, Zhao J, Wei X, Luo L, Chu Y, Zhang T, et al. Acupuncture may play a key role in anti-depression through various mechanisms in depression. *Chin Med*. 2024;19(1):135. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13020-024-00990-2>
14. Sun B, Cao X, Xin M, Guan R. Treatment of Depression with Acupuncture Based on Pathophysiological Mechanism. *Int J Gen Med*. 2024;17:347-57. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/ijgm.S448031>
15. Xian J, Wang L, Sun M, Wang X, Zang X-M, Yu H-J, et al. Acupuncture for Subthreshold Depression: Study Protocol for a Randomized Controlled Trial. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*. 2022;Volume 12 - 2021.
16. Chen B, Wang CC, Lee KH, Xia JC, Luo Z. Efficacy and safety of acupuncture for depression: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Res Nurs Health*. 2023;46(1):48-67. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/nur.22284>
17. Cai W, Ma W, Li Y-J, Wang G-T, Yang H, Shen W-D. Efficacy and safety of electroacupuncture for post-stroke depression: a randomized controlled trial. *Acupuncture in Medicine*. 2022;40(5):434-42. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/09645284221077104>
18. Liu C, Zhao Y, Qin S, Wang X, Jiang Y, Wu W. Randomized controlled trial of acupuncture for anxiety and depression in patients with chronic insomnia. *Annals of Translational Medicine*. 2021;9(18):1426.
19. Yu X, Hua S, Jin E, Guo R, Huang H. Improving hemodialysis patient depression outcomes with acupuncture: A randomized controlled trial. *Acta Psychologica*. 2025;253:104728. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.104728>
20. Yin X, Li W, Wu H, Dong B, Ma J, Li S, et al. Efficacy of Electroacupuncture on Treating Depression-Related Insomnia: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Nature and science of sleep*. 2020;12:497-508. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2147/nss.S253320>
21. Zhang S-h, Wang Y-l, Zhang C-x, Zhang C-p, Xiao P, Li Q-f, et al. Effect of Interactive Dynamic Scalp Acupuncture on Post-Stroke Cognitive Function, Depression, and Anxiety: A Multicenter, Randomized, Controlled Trial. *Chinese journal of integrative medicine*. 2022;28(2):106-15. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11655-021-3338-1>
22. Li W, Sun M, Yin X, Lao L, Kuang Z, Xu S. The effect of acupuncture on depression and its correlation with metabolic alterations: A randomized controlled trial. *Medicine*. 2020;99(43).
23. Wang Y, Huang YW, Ablikim D, Lu Q, Zhang AJ, Dong YQ, et al. Efficacy of acupuncture at ghost points combined with fluoxetine in treating depression: A randomized study. *World J Clin Cases*. 2022;10(3):929-38. doi: <https://doi.org/10.12998/wjcc.v10.i3.929>
24. Garrido-Ardila EM, González-López-Arza MV, Jiménez-Palomares M, García-Nogales A, Rodríguez-Mansilla J. Effects of Physiotherapy vs. Acupuncture in Quality of Life, Pain, Stiffness, Difficulty to Work and Depression of Women with Fibromyalgia: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *J Clin Med*. 2021;10(17). doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm10173765>
25. Maciocia S. *The Practice of Chinese Medicine: The Treatment of Diseases with Acupuncture and Chinese Herbs*: Elsevier Health Sciences; 2021. 9780702079207.
26. Maciocia G. *The Psyche in Chinese Medicine: Treatment of Emotional and Mental Disharmonies with Acupuncture and Chinese Herbs*: Churchill Livingstone; 2009. 9780702047770.
27. Mao L, Lv FF, Yang WF, Zhang TF, Li ZC, Li DQ, et al. Effects of Baihui electroacupuncture in a rat model of depression. *Ann Transl Med*. 2020;8(24):1646. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-20-7459>

28. Gao J, Lai MY, Mai TT, Fu W, Wang MY, Ning BL, et al. [Effects of electroacupuncture on BDNF/mTORC1 signaling pathway and synaptic plasticity in prefrontal cortex of rats exposed to chronic unpredictable mild stress]. *Zhen ci yan jiu = Acupuncture research*. 2022;47(1):15-20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13702/j.1000-0607.201293>
29. Zhou F, Jiang H, Kong N, Lin J, Zhang F, Mai T, et al. Electroacupuncture Attenuated Anxiety and Depression-Like Behavior via Inhibition of Hippocampal Inflammatory Response and Metabolic Disorders in TNBS-Induced IBD Rats. *Oxidative Medicine and Cellular Longevity*. 2022;2022(1):8295580. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8295580>
30. Liu Y, Lee DH, Kosowicz E, Lin J, Ma L, Yao S, et al. Targeting mental health: A scoping review of acupoints selection in acupressure for depression, anxiety, and stress. *Brain Behavior and Immunity Integrative*. 2025;10:100111. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbii.2025.100111>
31. Zhao Z, Jin X, Wu Y, Yang X, Xu Y, Jiang JZ, et al. Amygdaloid corticotropin-releasing factor is involved in the anxiolytic effect of acupuncture during ethanol withdrawal in rats. *Journal of Acupuncture and Meridian Studies*. 2013;6(5):234-40.
32. Wang X, Wang Z, Liu J, Chen J, Liu X, Nie G, et al. Repeated acupuncture treatments modulate amygdala resting state functional connectivity of depressive patients. *NeuroImage: Clinical*. 2016;12:746-52.
33. Stephens MAC, Wand G. Stress and the HPA axis: role of glucocorticoids in alcohol dependence. *Alcohol research: current reviews*. 2012;34(4):468.
34. Kwon C-Y, Lee B. Acupuncture or acupressure on Yintang (EX-HN 3) for anxiety: a preliminary review. *Medical acupuncture*. 2018;30(2):73-9.
35. Du L, Song X-J, Li Z-W, Liao L-X, Zhu Y-H. [Combined use of Shenmen (HT 7) and Sanyinjiao (SP 6) to improve the anxiety and depression in patients with insomnia: a randomized controlled trial]. *Zhongguo zhen jiu = Chinese acupuncture & moxibustion*. 2022;42(1):13-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.13703/j.0255-2930.20210113-k0002>
36. Kim H, Park H-J, Han S-M, Hahm D-H, Lee H-J, Kim K-S, et al. The effects of acupuncture stimulation at PC6 (Neiguan) on chronic mild stress-induced biochemical and behavioral responses. *Neuroscience Letters*. 2009;460(1):56-60. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2009.05.008>
37. Lee B, Shim I, Lee H-J, Yang Y, Hahm D-H. Effects of acupuncture on chronic corticosterone-induced depression-like behavior and expression of neuropeptide Y in the rats. *Neuroscience Letters*. 2009;453(3):151-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2009.01.076>
38. Huang Q-f. Exploration of the clinical regularity of acupuncture-moxibustion treatment for depression. *Journal of Acupuncture and Tuina Science*. 2009;7(1):57-60. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11726-009-0057-0>